

Stress, Burnout, and Coping Strategies among Nurses Working in Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs): An Exploratory Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Nurses working in Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs) are exposed to highly demanding clinical, emotional, and organizational conditions. The continuous care of critically ill newborns, the interaction with families, and the ethical complexity of neonatal intensive care may contribute to perceived stress, anxiety, and burnout, potentially affecting both occupational well-being and quality of care.

Objective: This exploratory cross-sectional study aimed to assess perceived stress, burnout, anxiety, and coping strategies among nurses working in NICUs, and to examine the relationships between burnout dimensions and coping mechanisms.

Methods: Thirty-seven nurses working in the NICU departments of San Marco and Garibaldi hospitals in Catania, Italy, were enrolled between February and June 2023. Participants completed a socio-demographic form and validated psychometric questionnaires, including the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI), the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI-Y1 and STAI-Y2), and the Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced – New Italian Version (COPE-NVI). Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated to examine associations between burnout, perceived stress, anxiety, coping strategies, and demographic variables. Cumulative Proportional Odds Models were used to identify possible predictors of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment.

Results: Nearly half of the sample reported high levels of perceived stress. Burnout-related symptoms were frequently observed, particularly emotional exhaustion and depersonalization. Perceived stress was significantly associated with higher emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, and with lower personal accomplishment. State and trait anxiety also showed significant relationships with specific burnout dimensions. Among coping strategies, avoidance was significantly associated with perceived stress and emerged as a relevant predictor of burnout-related outcomes in the ordinal regression models.

Conclusions: The findings suggest that nurses working in NICUs may experience clinically relevant levels of perceived stress and burnout. Avoidance coping appears to be a maladaptive strategy associated with worse psychological outcomes. Interventions aimed at strengthening adaptive coping, emotional regulation, resilience, and organizational support may help reduce burnout and promote occupational well-being among NICU nurses.

Keywords: Anxiety; burnout; coping strategies; neonatal intensive care unit; NICU; nurses; occupational stress; perceived stress; psychological well-being.

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INTRODUCTION

In the healthcare field, work-related stress and burnout syndrome are prevalent among the nursing profession [1]. This is due to factors inherent in the "helping professions," such as prolonged contact with illness and suffering, as well as organizational reasons like work overload, role conflict, a lack of perceived equity, minimal involvement in decision-making processes, inadequate recognition, and insufficient social support [2]. Numerous medical and nursing studies have reported the effects of workload, environment, and life circumstances contributing to burnout [1-5]. These effects can include job dissatisfaction, poor quality of life, and adverse patient outcomes. This aspect becomes particularly significant for nurses, who are highly exposed to burnout, as highlighted by various studies both in Italy and abroad [1-6]. Nurses directly interact with patients, their families, and the multidisciplinary team. In general, it has been highlighted that the perception of stress in nurses is indeed high. Moreover, the specific working conditions faced by this professional group cause an erosion of the willingness to help patients (burn-out), high turnover, and a significant level of drop-out, especially among young nursing trainees [2,3,5,6].

Particularly affected are emergency departments, especially when service users are vulnerable, like in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) [7-9]. The NICU is a specialized department providing intensive and sub-intensive care to paediatric patients in critical conditions, generally newborns under 30 days old with congenital complications, premature birth, or severe illnesses that threaten their lives [9]. These units are in hospitals with Level I and II Emergency Departments, National Hospitals of High Specialization, or IRCCS Institutes, due to their high specialization and complex care requirements. Advanced technologies and equipment, such as neonatal incubators, phototherapy lamps for hyperbilirubinemia treatment, mechanical lung ventilators, and invasive monitoring systems for cases of birth

asphyxia and severe respiratory failure, are used in the NICU. This results in a higher operational budget compared to other units within the same hospital, but often the staff is less than the actual needs. Typically, the NICU is divided into two areas: the intensive and sub-intensive areas. The intensive area cares for patients with severe diseases or extreme prematurity, at risk of life or with severe consequences [10,11]. These infants require high-intensity care, such as respiratory support, therapeutic hypothermia, administration of specific drugs, transfusions, and central venous catheters for parenteral nutrition. In the sub-intensive area, patients who no longer need intensive or ventilatory care are hosted but require constant monitoring of vital parameters [10,11]. In this section, infants improve their nutritional abilities until they reach adequate growth for discharge. During this phase, parents play a fundamental role, learning the necessary skills to manage the newborn at home. However, the ethical dilemma often encountered in these units is having to save the lives of newborns at all costs while ensuring their survival. This can lead to problems related to therapeutic obstinacy, invasiveness of care, and the need to inflict suffering to save the child's life. Additionally, the question arises of the limits to which one can go in terms of care and the stakes involved in these decisions [12].

Early recognition of burnout is crucial for assessing stress response methods and improving organization within the operational unit. The best prevention for burnout among intensive care unit operators focuses on the mental, emotional, and psychological well-being of the workers [4-6,12]. Despite nursing being a profession based on altruism and empathy, it seems that operators prefer coping strategies less based on emotions and more on rational analysis of the problem. This could be since managing emotions requires significant effort and can lead to greater emotional exhaustion [2,3].

Coping strategies, i.e., the mental and behavioural strategies for dealing with stress, can reduce or prevent burnout if used timely and appropriately. Understanding these strategies and how they can be modified over time is important, both for the operators themselves and for those managing human resources. Recommendations for mitigating burnout include self-care, promoting organizational well-being, career development, and leadership support [3].

The purpose of this study is to assess stress and the incidence of burnout syndrome in NICU nurses and determine the existing correlations with the coping mechanisms employed.

METHODS

Study participants

In this study, thirty-seven healthcare staff members (mean \pm SD: 36.74 \pm 7.7) were enrolled from the NICU departments of San Marco and Garibaldi hospitals in Catania during the period from February to June 2023. This study was conducted in accordance with the "Declaration of Helsinki of 1964." Participants consented to complete the questionnaires anonymously, through a consent form derived from privacy law ("Legislative Decree June 30, 2003, No. 196" "Code regarding the protection of personal data"). Each healthcare worker was included in the study if they had worked in the neonatal intensive care department for at least one year and had conducted both day shifts (from 7:00 to 14:00 or 14:00-21:00) and night shifts (from 21:00 to 7:00). The participants were relatively experienced in NICU work.

Outcomes measures

All participants completed an information form for the collection of demographic data and the following anonymous questionnaires: the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) [13]; the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) [14]; the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) Y1 (state) and Y2 (trait) [15]; and the Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced – New Italian Version (COPE-NVI) [16]. The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) by Maslach and Jackson (1981), is widely used in the professional field to assess the level of burnout among operators. The three dimensions measured by the MBI are considered important indicators for understanding the syndrome: emotional exhaustion reflects the feeling of

exhaustion and lack of energy due to work; depersonalization refers to a distant and impersonal response towards the users of the work carried out; personal accomplishment measures the sense of competence and personal satisfaction experienced in the workplace. The questionnaire consists of 22 items that ask people to evaluate the frequency with which they experience certain feelings related to burnout, with responses provided on a Likert scale ranging from 0 (never) to 6 (every day). Numerous studies have confirmed the validity of the MBI. The Italian version of the MBI, developed by Pedrabissi and Santinello in 1999 [17], has been shown to have a structure like Maslach's original version.

The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is a psychological tool used to measure operators' perception of stress in response to life events. The items were constructed to capture the level to which test respondents find their lives unpredictable, uncontrollable, or overloaded. The scale also includes a series of direct questions about current levels of perceived stress and regarding feelings and thoughts related to the last month. The possible responses are indicated on a scale from 0 to 4, where 0 represents "never" and 4 "very often"; the instrument's total scores can vary from 0 to 40, with higher scores indicating a higher perception of stress. The STAI - form Y, is a self-report questionnaire, widely used in research and clinical practice, and considered a reliable and valid tool for assessing anxiety. The total score can range from 20 to 80 for each of the two scales: the first focuses on "state anxiety" (STAI-Y1), which refers to a transient state of concern and unease and assesses the anxiety experienced at the time of the test administration; the second is related to "trait anxiety" (STAI-Y2), i.e., a psychological dimension where the subject is prone to anxious reactions under specific conditions. In the STAI-Y1 scale, the subject is invited to indicate on a four-point scale (1. Not at all, 2. A little, 3. Quite a bit, 4. Very much) how they feel at the time of completion; while in the STAI-Y2 scale, the subject is asked to indicate on a four-point scale (1. Almost never, 2. Sometimes, 3. Often, 4. Almost always) how they usually feel, habitually. The response is marked by the subject with a cross, and the administration time is about 10-15 minutes.

The COPE-NVI, finally, is a useful and psychometrically valid tool for measuring coping styles in the Italian context. Its original version contained 52 items divided into 13 scales, each consisting of 4 items: the first 5 were about problem-focused coping, the next 5 were about emotion-focused coping, and the last 3 expressed avoidance and resignation. The Italian version consists of 60 items divided into five independent dimensions: Social Support, 11 items referring to seeking understanding, information, and emotional venting; Avoidance Strategies, 16 items including the use of denial, substance use, and behavioral and mental detachment; Positive Attitude (12 items) regarding the adoption of an attitude of acceptance, containment, and positive reinterpretation of events; Problem Orientation, consisting of 12 items and involves the use of active strategies and planning; and Transcendent Orientation, composed of 8 items, referring to religion and the absence of humour. The questionnaire is self-assessed and requires the subject to express their degree of agreement or disagreement with each item on a four-point Likert scale (1. I usually do not do it, 2. I do it sometimes, 3. I do it quite often, 4. I do it almost always), based on the frequency with which they use certain coping strategies in stressful situations.

Study procedures

Participation in the research was proposed to the NICU nurses after a brief explanation of the concept of burnout, emphasizing the work-related and other consequences associated with it. Participation was completely voluntary and after joining the project and completing the information form and informed consent, participants independently completed the MBI questionnaire, the PSS scale, the STAI, and the COPE-NVI test. The timing and methods of carrying out this project did not interfere with the normal conduct of work shifts.

Statistical analyses

Categorical variables were reported as absolute frequencies and percentages, while numerical variables were reported as mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values. A parametric approach was applied because the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test provided evidence of an approximately normal distribution for most of the variables analyzed, despite the limited sample size. Pearson’s correlation coefficients were calculated to examine associations between psychometric measures, including MBI, PSS, STAI-Y1, STAI-Y2, and COPE-NVI scores, and demographic variables. Scatterplots were created to visualize the main correlations.

To identify possible predictors of the outcomes of interest, namely emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment, cumulative proportional odds models were estimated, as the response variables were ordinal with three levels: low, medium, and high. These models were implemented using the Polytomous Universal Model procedure in SPSS. For each model, Cox and Snell, Nagelkerke, and McFadden pseudo-R² indices were calculated to assess model fit.

Circular diagrams and boxplots were created to visualize the distribution of data according to specific categories of the outcomes of interest. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS for Windows, version 22.0.

RESULTS

A total of 37 nurses participated in the study. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the numerical variables considered for the study.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics and psychometric scores of the study sample.

Variable	Value
Demographic characteristics	
Sample, n (%)	37 (100.0)
Female, n (%)	33 (89.2)
Male, n (%)	4 (10.8)
Age, years, mean ± SD	40.14 ± 13.25
Single, n (%)	19 (51.4)
Married/cohabiting, n (%)	18 (48.6)
With children, n (%)	17 (45.9)
Without children, n (%)	20 (54.1)
Years of service, mean ± SD	14.97 ± 13.23
Psychometric scores	
MBI-EE, mean ± SD	16.92 ± 11.00
MBI-DP, mean ± SD	4.24 ± 4.94
MBI-PA, mean ± SD	36.00 ± 7.01
MBI total score, mean ± SD	57.16 ± 13.68
PSS, mean ± SD	15.16 ± 6.10
STAI-Y1, mean ± SD	38.35 ± 8.78

STAI-Y2, mean \pm SD	37.97 \pm 7.29
COPE-SS, mean \pm SD	29.43 \pm 6.97
COPE-AS, mean \pm SD	22.49 \pm 5.75
COPE-PA, mean \pm SD	32.68 \pm 5.47
COPE-PO, mean \pm SD	31.97 \pm 7.15
COPE-TO, mean \pm SD	23.35 \pm 4.90

Note: Continuous variables are reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD); categorical variables are reported as absolute frequencies and percentages. MBI: Maslach Burnout Inventory; EE: Emotional Exhaustion; DP: Depersonalization; PA: Personal Accomplishment; PSS: Perceived Stress Scale; STAI-Y1: State Anxiety; STAI-Y2: Trait Anxiety; COPE-NVI: Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced – New Italian Version; SS: Social Support; AS: Avoidance Strategies; PA: Positive Attitude; PO: Problem Orientation; TO: Transcendent Orientation.

Figure 1, on the other hand, show the frequencies for categorical variables such as gender, marital status, and children. Subsequently, the relative frequencies obtained from the individual scales administered to the sample were analyzed, followed by an analysis of their correlations. Relative frequencies for the MBI, SSP, and STAI-Y: 43.2% of the sample scored low on the Emotional Exhaustion subscale of the MBI; 27% scored medium, and 29.7% scored high. 56.8% of the sample scored low on the Depersonalization subscale of the MBI; 10.8% scored medium, and 32.4% scored high. Finally, 37.8% of the sample scored low on the Personal Accomplishment subscale of the MBI; 32.4% scored medium, and 29.7% scored high. (Figure 1). 51.4% of the sample scored within the normal range for the SSP, and 48.6% scored high. Following this, examining the percentages obtained for the STAI - Y1 referring to state anxiety and the STAI - Y2 referring to trait anxiety, we can observe that only 21.6% of the sample scored below 30 on the STAI - Y1, related to state anxiety, while the remaining 78.4% scored high (> 30). In fact, 18.9% of the sample scored between 45 and 56 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentual distribution of categorical variables in the sample.

Correlation between MBI, demographic data PSS, and STAI Y1/Y2

To analyze the relationship between the scores obtained on the MBI questionnaire (total and its three subscales EE, DP, and RP) and the demographic data of the subjects, PSS, and STAI Y1/Y2, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated (see Table 2).

Table 2. Correlations between burnout dimensions, demographic characteristics, perceived stress, anxiety, and coping strategies.

Ariable	MBI-EE	MBI-DP	MBI-PA	MBI total
Age	0.189 (0.264)	0.008 (0.965)	0.160 (0.344)	0.236 (0.159)
Years of service	0.223 (0.185)	0.035 (0.839)	0.193 (0.253)	0.291 (0.081)
Marital status	-0.172 (0.310)	-0.051 (0.763)	-0.110 (0.519)	-0.213 (0.206)
Children	-0.227 (0.177)	-0.054 (0.750)	-0.141 (0.404)	-0.274 (0.100)
PSS	0.565 (<0.001)	0.374 (0.022)	-0.391 (0.017)	0.389 (0.017)
STAI-Y1	0.390 (0.017)	0.179 (0.288)	-0.347 (0.035)	0.201 (0.233)
STAI-Y2	0.433 (0.007)	0.114 (0.503)	-0.272 (0.104)	0.250 (0.135)
COPE-SS	0.164 (0.331)	0.146 (0.388)	0.011 (0.949)	0.190 (0.259)
COPE-AS	0.293 (0.078)	0.175 (0.300)	-0.202 (0.230)	0.195 (0.246)

COPE-PosA	0.055 (0.749)	0.067 (0.694)	0.128 (0.449)	0.134 (0.430)
COPE-PO	-0.018 (0.916)	0.019 (0.911)	0.140 (0.408)	0.064 (0.706)
COPE-TO	-0.074 (0.665)	-0.191 (0.258)	0.309 (0.063)	0.030 (0.859)

Note: Values are reported as Pearson's correlation coefficients with p-values in parentheses. Statistically significant correlations are shown in bold. MBI: Maslach Burnout Inventory; EE: Emotional Exhaustion; DP: Depersonalization; PA: Personal Accomplishment; PSS: Perceived Stress Scale; STAI-Y1: State Anxiety; STAI-Y2: Trait Anxiety; COPE-NVI: Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced – New Italian Version; SS: Social Support; AS: Avoidance Strategies; PosA: Positive Attitude; PO: Problem Orientation; TO: Transcendent Orientation.

As regard to the correlation between MBI, PSS, and STAI, Pearson's correlation revealed a positive correlation between perceived stress (PSS) and burnout (MBI) in all three dimensions (EE, DP, and RP); a significant correlation between the State Anxiety scale (STAI-Y1) with the perception of Personal Accomplishment (MBI-RP), and the Emotional Exhaustion subscale (MBI-EE). The latter is also correlated with the Trait Anxiety scale (STAI-Y2).

Moreover, concerning the correlation between MBI and coping strategies, we observed that the correlation between the scores obtained on the MBI by the NICU nurses and the Coping strategies, the results indicate a slight correlation between the avoidance strategies of the COPE scale and the emotional exhaustion of the MBI. Furthermore, we found a slight correlation between Transcendent Orientation and Personal Accomplishment.

Correlation between coping strategies and demographic data of the sample, PSS, STAI-Y1/Y2

The results show a significantly positive correlation between age, years of service, and marital status of the participants with the Social Support scale, related to the search for emotional venting. Moreover, it was found that the age of the participants positively correlates with the Transcendent Orientation strategy, related to religion and the absence of humour. Finally, marital status also positively correlates with the Positive Attitude scale, or simply positive thinking.

Moreover, the correlation between coping strategies was observed. Among the Coping strategies adopted, the Avoidance strategy shows a significant correlation with perceived stress (PSS), where the presence of high stress is linked to strategies that lead to avoiding the problem, minimizing it, or creating emotional detachment from it, resulting in an inability to effectively confront it. State Anxiety (STAI-Y1) also significantly correlates with the Avoidance strategy, but also with the Positive Attitude and Transcendent Orientation.

Finally, we can note a correlation between the Trait Anxiety scale (STAI-Y2), a more stable dimension of the subject, with all Coping strategies (SE, AP, OP, OT), except for the Social Support strategy. For more details, see Table 3.

Table 3. Correlations between coping strategies, demographic characteristics, perceived stress, and anxiety.

Variable	COPE-SS	COPE-AS	COPE-PosA	COPE-PO	COPE-TO
Age	-0.402 (0.014)	0.172 (0.309)	-0.103 (0.544)	0.057 (0.735)	0.442 (0.006)
Years of service	-0.384 (0.019)	0.199 (0.238)	-0.052 (0.760)	0.083 (0.624)	0.411 (0.012)
Marital status	0.368 (0.025)	-0.031 (0.856)	0.383 (0.019)	0.280 (0.093)	-0.265 (0.113)
PSS	0.132 (0.435)	0.460 (0.004)	-0.199 (0.237)	-0.271 (0.105)	-0.276 (0.098)
STAI-Y1	0.247 (0.140)	0.329 (0.047)	-0.352 (0.033)	-0.292 (0.080)	-0.417 (0.010)
STAI-Y2	0.300 (0.072)	0.474 (0.003)	-0.349 (0.035)	-0.328 (0.047)	-0.391 (0.017)

Note: Values are reported as Pearson’s correlation coefficients, with p-values in parentheses. Statistically significant correlations are shown in bold. COPE-NVI: Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced – New Italian Version; SS: Social Support; AS: Avoidance Strategies; PosA: Positive Attitude; PO: Problem Orientation; TO: Transcendent Orientation; PSS: Perceived Stress Scale; STAI-Y1: State Anxiety; STAI-Y2: Trait Anxiety.

Finally, no significant correlation was found between STAI-Y1/Y2 and the demographic data of the sample. STAI-Y1 and STAI-Y2 were significantly and positively correlated with PSS (Table 4).

Table 4. Correlations between anxiety, demographic characteristics, and perceived stress.

Variable	STAI-Y1	STAI-Y2
Age	-0.164 (0.333)	-0.043 (0.801)
Years of service	-0.167 (0.324)	-0.046 (0.788)
Marital status	-0.054 (0.750)	0.026 (0.877)
Children	0.000 (0.999)	-0.094 (0.580)
PSS	0.703 (<0.001)	0.578 (<0.001)

Note: Values are reported as Pearson’s correlation coefficients, with p-values in parentheses. Statistically significant correlations are shown in bold. STAI-Y1: State Anxiety; STAI-Y2: Trait Anxiety; PSS: Perceived Stress Scale.

Predictive factors of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal fulfillment

Finally, we aimed to identify possible predictors of three outcomes of interest, by using Cumulative Proportional Odds Models. In each of the three models the following covariates were tested: Age, years of work, the different coping strategies (specifically: COPE_SS, COPE_SE, COPE_AP, COPE_OP, COPE_OT), gender (male vs female), and sons (yes vs no). Examining the results obtained from the Cumulative Proportional Odds Model estimation (Table 5), the COPE SE appears to exert a positive and significant influence on the three outcomes of interest, Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization and also Personal Fulfillment (Figure 2).

On this last outcome, another variable appears to exert a significant influence, the COPE SS; more specifically, the negative sign of the coefficient denotes that higher values of COPE SS correspond to a lower degree of personal fulfillment. For more details, see table 5. For each estimated model, Cox and Snell test, Nagelkerke test and McFadden test provided evidence about a good degree of model fit to the observed data, thus denoting the adequacy of the chosen model.

Table 5. Cumulative proportional odds models for burnout-related outcomes.

Outcome	Independent variable	Estimate	95% CI lower	95% CI upper	Wald	p-value
Emotional exhaustion	Constant 1	-3.177	-11.556	5.202	0.552	0.457
	Constant 2	-1.740	-10.084	6.603	0.167	0.683
	Age	-0.143	-0.344	0.059	1.920	0.166
	Years of service	0.115	-0.070	0.300	1.494	0.222
	COPE-SS	-0.003	-0.122	0.117	0.002	0.961
	COPE-AS	0.117	0.043	0.278	2.062	0.041

	COPE-PosA	0.044	-0.133	0.222	0.238	0.625
	COPE-PO	-0.076	-0.203	0.051	1.370	0.242
	COPE-TO	-0.046	-0.231	0.138	0.244	0.622
	Gender, male vs female	2.329	1.042	4.701	3.706	0.045
	Children, yes vs no	0.958	-2.533	4.449	0.289	0.591
Depersonalization	Constant 1	5.197	-3.985	14.379	1.231	0.267
	Constant 2	5.765	-3.454	14.984	1.502	0.220
	Age	-0.068	-0.272	0.136	0.423	0.515
	Years of service	0.071	-0.125	0.267	0.509	0.475
	COPE-SS	0.067	-0.060	0.193	1.076	0.300
	COPE-AS	0.102	0.069	0.273	1.362	0.042
	COPE-PosA	0.126	-0.083	0.336	1.404	0.236
	COPE-PO	-0.048	-0.182	0.087	0.482	0.487
	COPE-TO	-0.024	-0.223	0.174	0.058	0.809
	Gender, male vs female	1.910	-0.452	4.271	2.513	0.113
	Children, yes vs no	0.062	-3.424	3.547	0.001	0.972
Personal accomplishment	Constant 1	-1.243	-9.141	6.655	0.095	0.758
	Constant 2	0.663	-7.234	8.561	0.027	0.869
	Age	0.100	-0.100	0.300	0.961	0.327
	Years of service	-0.086	-0.273	0.101	0.817	0.366
	COPE-SS	-0.128	-0.266	-0.010	3.286	0.047
	COPE-AS	0.282	0.041	0.523	5.253	0.022
	COPE-PosA	-0.079	-0.276	0.118	0.617	0.432
	COPE-PO	0.018	-0.115	0.150	0.067	0.796
	COPE-TO	-0.107	-0.294	0.080	1.255	0.263
	Gender, male vs female	0.462	-1.967	2.891	0.139	0.709
	Children, yes vs no	-3.117	-7.125	0.891	2.324	0.127

Note: Cumulative Proportional Odds Models were estimated for the three burnout-related outcomes. Statistically significant associations are shown in bold. CI: confidence interval; COPE-NVI: Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced – New Italian Version; SS: Social Support; AS: Avoidance Strategies; PosA: Positive Attitude; PO: Problem Orientation; TO: Transcendent Orientation.

Figure 2. Boxplot of COPE SE distribution according to categories for outcomes of interest.

DISCUSSION

The results obtained contribute to the literature, which is lacking and contradictory regarding burnout syndrome in NICU departments [8-12, 20-23]. Our findings highlight positive correlations between stress and burnout in all three dimensions, namely emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. This result is consistent with the literature on burnout among nurses in general [1-4] and in NICU departments in particular [12].

We observed that nearly half of the sample (48.6%) subjected to the study tested positive for perceived stress. Moreover, most of them are in a state of burnout (56.7%), with a high degree of emotional exhaustion (29.7%) and elevated depersonalization (32.4%). Only 29.7% of the neonatal intensive care nurses feel accomplished. In particular, attention was paid to the coping strategies of the nurses, which showed an average result of 139 (min: 96; max: 210 points), a score obtained from the sum of the individual dimensions of the COPE-NVI, and considered as an index of how the individual reacts to stress: the higher the score obtained, the greater the ability to cope with the stressful situation. This data is comparable to that of a study conducted in 2015 at the Valle D'Aosta Company where good psychological well-being of the territorial area of Valle D'Aosta operators compared to the hospital area was brought to light [24].

In relation to burnout syndrome, our study showed only a slight correlation between the Emotional Exhaustion subscale of the MBI and the Avoidance strategy of the COPE scale. The Avoidance strategy shows a statistically significant relationship with perceived stress; therefore, the presence of high stress is linked to strategies that lead to avoiding the problem, minimizing it, creating emotional detachment from it, resulting in an inability to effectively confront it. State Anxiety also significantly correlates with the Avoidance strategy, but also with Positive Attitude and Transcendent Orientation. Trait Anxiety, on the other hand, a more stable dimension of the subject indicating his habitual enacted behavior, correlates with all Coping strategies, such as, besides the Avoidance strategy, Positive Attitude, Problem Orientation, and Transcendent Orientation, except however for the Social Support strategy. The latter, related to emotional venting, in turn positively correlates with the demographic data of the sample, in particular age, years of service, and marital status.

Furthermore, we observed that the age of the participants also positively correlates with the Transcendent Orientation strategy, related to religion and the absence of humor; this means that as the age of the subject increases,

he will be more inclined to use this strategy. Marital status, finally, correlates with the Positive Attitude scale, or simply positive thinking. However, by calculating the average of the individual dimensions of the COPE-NVI, we can affirm how the strategies most used by NICU nurses in the Catania area appear to be those related to Positive Attitude (average score 32.68 with a standard deviation of 5.47) and Problem Orientation (31.97; SD 7.15), a strategy with which the subject, using their own resources, aims to solve the problem; as well as Social Support (29.43; SD 6.97). Similarly, there is a lesser tendency to use strategies pertaining to Transcendent Orientation (M 23.35; SD 4.9) and Avoidance (M 22.49; SD 5.75).

Concerning states of anxiety, also analyzed, the average of the sample under study obtained a score of 38.35 for state anxiety and 37.97 for trait anxiety. A maximum correlation between perceived stress and both states of anxiety was found. Nonetheless, the hypothesis of other study related the presence of a correlation between burnout and anxiety is confirmed [3,23,25,26].

We maintain, for the purposes of the study and as demonstrated by it that burnout is a widespread phenomenon among nurses, particularly in NICU departments. The health of young patients and organizations originates from the mental, physical, and psychological well-being of the operators: establishing the Coping strategies that health professionals perceive as effective is essential to confront stress, and consequently, the burnout syndrome related to it [25,26]. Based on what has been said so far, we advise against the use of avoidance strategies, which include the use of substances, behavioral and mental detachment, or the use of denial, significantly correlated with perceived stress, and demonstrated to be so by Portero [25]. Furthermore, we believe it is optimal to use interventions that promote coping strategies [4, 26-30] based on a positive attitude, namely the adoption of an attitude of acceptance and positive reinterpretation of events, being optimistic, resilient, possessing a good psychological capital or psyCap. The development of self-care strategies intended as finding meaning in work, connecting with a source of energy, nurturing interpersonal connections, developing an attitude of positivity, or recognizing one's uniqueness and contribution to work, helps to protect and support the well-being of healthcare workers and reduce burnout, as also demonstrated by the study conducted by Wei et al. [26].

Our study has some limitations. First, the small sample size does not allow for the generalization of the obtained data. For this reason, this study has been intended as a pilot study. Furthermore, the lack of follow-up and the failure to consider other variables that could have influenced the results. However, our study is to be understood as a preliminary study to highlight the risk situation of nurses.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our results encourage the adoption of interventions aimed at intervening on the emotional state of operators, using adequate coping strategies, based on the implementation of resilience and well-being, and on the reduction of burnout levels, as with mindfulness-based interventions [31-35]. As highlighted by our study, burnout can be significantly high in nurses in departments with high empathetic involvement [30], such as NICU, and this requires policies for the prevention and promotion of the well-being and psychological health of nurses.

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